

IMPROVED ADAPTIVE NEURO-FUZZY INFERENCE MODEL FOR PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER FORECAST

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Abstract-Photovoltaic (PV) systems are recently the most used sustainable energy source to fit with the energy demand growth. Generally, batteries, as storage systems, are installed along with PV modules. When it comes to an optimal power management of PV/battery hybrid systems, the uncertain and intermittent behavior of PV power production can provoke some challenges, with which, the real-time operation of the hybrid system can be degraded, therefore, PV power forecast is highly needed. Data-driven models are became nowadays very efficient methods to build regression models for the purpose of PV power forecast. In this paper, Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference (ANFIS) is chosen as a data-driven technique, to build up forecasting models. Standard ANFIS, which uses only weather data, cannot avoid the confusing scenarios like PV modules covered by the snow in clear-sky days. This work proposes an improved ANFIS model taking historical generated power into account. The developed model is validated on a real case, using the PV system of the institute of energy system technologies in Offenburg. When adding the average of produced power of the last 72 hours as additional input, the model was able to follow the rapid changes in weather conditions and overcome the unexceptional situations like the problem of snow on the PV modules.

Keywords-photovoltaic power forecast, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference, photovoltaic/battery hybrid systems management.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, there has been a growing interest on weather forecast in many applications. This task is highly recommended when optimal energy management is targeted for systems integrating renewable resources. When it comes to islanded photovoltaic (PV)-based microgrids (MG), PV power forecast is a fundamental task [1-3], surplus PV generation can occur overvoltage at the connection points even with optimal design of PV systems. In case of connected storage system, PV system can cause frequent fast and deep charging/discharging scenarios, which may decrease the batteries life-time. Having enough information about the future PV production can make it possible avoiding all the mentioned challenges. Generally, PV power is predictable when enough information about the insolation and temperature is available, this data is usually provided thanks to many online services available on internet.

PV generation forecast methods can be broadly classified into four approaches: statistical approach, Artificial Intelligence (AI) approach, physical approach and hybrid approach [4]. Statistical approaches are based on data-driven formulation using historical measured data to forecast solar time series [5]. AI approaches utilize advanced AI techniques, such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), to construct solar forecasters, which can be also classified into the category of the statistical approach [6]. Physical models are based on numerical weather prediction or satellite images that predict solar irradiance and PV generation [7], [8]. Finally, hybrid approaches are combination of the three afore-mentioned methods [9]. In practice, different forecasting approaches are preferred depending on different scales of prediction

horizons to meet the requirements of the decision-making process [10].

In the case of PV plant, the power generation mechanism depends on several factors like the number and model of solar cells; number of installed modules; positioning and inclination of modules; instantaneous values of solar irradiation and temperature. Unlike other factors, insolation and temperature are not constants, they are varying and fluctuating all the time in an uncertain behavior, which makes it a challenging for any forecast method to follow up the real produced power.

Different prediction horizons will correspond to the specific needs of decision-making activities in a MG as follows [11]:

1. Short-term (between 24 and 72 hours ahead): Such forecasts are crucial for different decision-making problems involved in the electricity market and power system operation, including economic dispatch, unit commitment, etc.
2. Medium-term (up to one week ahead): Medium-term forecasting would be useful for e.g., maintenance scheduling of PV plants, conventional power plants, transformers, and transmission lines.
3. Long-term (up to months to years): Long-term prediction/estimation can be applied for long-term solar energy assessment and PV plant planning.

Introduced by Jang in 1993 [12], Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference (ANFIS), belongs to AI approach, are among the candidates for PV power forecast development. This marriage of learning capability of neural network and knowledge representation ability of fuzzy logic has given

birth to fuzzy neural networks. As a result, the drawback of neural network black box inability to explain decision (lack of transparency), and weakness of learning in fuzzy logic have been conquered. In this paper, and for a particular PV system, different ANFIS models with different parameters are built up using two main inputs: real-time information of solar irradiation and temperature.

In cold zones, after snowing periods, PV modules could stay covered by the snow for a long time even during the followed sunny days, which makes it confusing for standard ANFIS models, that are based solely on insolation/temperature information, to predict the generated PV power. To overcome this challenge, this paper suggests the usage of an improved ANFIS regression model by providing enough information about historical changes in power production. In this fact, additional input is to be added which is the average of produced power for the last few hours. As a validation case, real dataset for a 6.3 KWp PV system, installed in the institute of energy system technologies (INES) in Offenburg, is used (Fig. 1). The general characteristics of INES PV system is listed in Table 1. First, a standard ANFIS model, using only insolation and temperature as inputs, is developed and simulated. Then, the same simulation scenario will be executed for an ANFIS model integrating an additional input, which is the average of produced power during the last 72 hours.

Table 1. INES PV power system parameters

	Parameter	Value
PV power system	Number of modules	27
	Inclination	9 x 35° 18 x 30°
	Alignment	180° south
	Power	6.3 kWp
PV module	Power at mpp Pmpp	240 Wp
	Voltage at mpp Vmpp	30.0 V
	Current at mpp Impp	8.1 A
	Open circuit voltage Voc	37.4 V
	Short circuit current Isc	8.6 A
	Temperature coefficient	-0.46 %/K

	model	Bosch solar module c-Si M 60
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Fig. 1. INES 6.3 kWp PV generator

The rest of the paper is organized as follow: in Section II, more explanation about the structure of a default ANFIS model is presented; in Section III, ANFIS standard forecast model is explained with a simulation study; while Section IV will be the stage for simulating the improved ANFIS model.

II. ADAPTIVE NEURO-FUZZY INFERENCE

The success of ANFIS can be attributed to the robustness of results it provides. ANFIS has as highly generalization capability as neural networks and other machine learning techniques [13-15]. It is based on Takagi-Sugeno-Kang model, or simply Sugeno fuzzy model, proposed by [16] where a rule R_k can be represented as:

$$R_k: \text{IF } \mu_{A_i}(x) \text{ AND } \mu_{B_i}(y) \text{ THEN } f = p_k x + q_k y + r_k \tag{1}$$

Where k is the number of rules, A_i and B_i are n fuzzy membership functions of any shape i.e., gaussian, triangular, trapezoidal, etc., denoted by μ in the antecedent part of the rule R_k , and p_k, q_k, r_k are the linear parameters of consequent part of the k^{th} rule. The parameters of membership functions (antecedent or premise parameters) and consequent part of the rule (consequent parameters) are tuned during the training process.

In this article, ANFIS five-layers architecture comprises of two types of nodes: fixed and adaptable (Fig. 2). The nodes in membership function layer and consequent layer are tunable, the rest of the nodes are fixed. In Layer 1, the node i is a membership function i.e., triangle, trapezoidal, or gaussian, etc. For example, if μ_{A_1}, μ_{A_2} and μ_{B_1}, μ_{B_2} are the membership functions of gaussian shape with two parameters center (c) and width (σ). Layer 2 calculates the firing strength of a rule via product Π operation. Layer 3 is normalized firing strength of a rule from previous layer. In Layer 4, each node represents consequent part of fuzzy

rule. The linear coefficients of rule consequent are trainable. Nodes in Layer 5 perform defuzzification of consequent part of rules by summing outputs of all the rules. Further detail on computation performed in ANFIS can be found in the related paper [16].

Fig. 2. ANFIS architecture

ANFIS learns by tuning all its tunable parameters (c, σ and p_k, q_k, r_k) in order to map input to the desired output with minimum error. The default ANFIS learning algorithm employs gradient descent (GD) for tuning membership functions and least square estimation (LSE) for training the consequent parameters. it is a two pass learning process as presented in Table 2.

The two pass learning algorithm tunes consequent parameters by LSE in forward pass and while back-propagating error back to first layer, it updates membership functions using GD. Since, GD is influenced by back propagation (BP) algorithm of ANN, which has the drawback to be likely trapped in local minima. On the other hand, the convergence of gradient method is also very slow; depending on initial parameter values.

Table 2. Two-Pass ANFIS Learning Algorithm

	Forward Pass	Backward Pass
Antecedent Parameters	Fixed	GD
Consequent Parameters	LSE	Fixed
Signals	Node Output	Error Signals

III. ANFIS FORECAST MODEL

In this section, standard Sugeno fuzzy-based model, that uses solar irradiation and temperature as inputs, is studied and validated. In the context of higher supervisory layer for INES experimental MG, the developed model is to be implemented on a high performance hardware solution like industrial computer, this later will then communicate with the Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), that manages the whole MG prototype, in the framework of a smart energy management. In INES experimental MG, weather data is accessible thanks to

online service called *Deutscher Wetterdienst*. It provides up to 3-day ahead with one-hour resolution.

Bellow, the ANFIS training process is explained, in which, four months dataset for Offenburg region, from September 2016 to January 2017, is downloaded from the local database. For testing, two weeks from February 2017 selected, these weeks are characterized by a rapid switching between snowing and sunning days. Figs 3, 4 and 5, and Table 3 show the characteristics of the chosen training data. As a development platform, MATLAB version R2014a, with Neuro-Fuzzy Designer toolbox is used on Intel® Core (TM)2 Duo CPU. The training parameters are chosen with default values.

Fig. 3. Hourly insolation in the training dataset.

Fig. 4. Hourly temperature in the training dataset

Fig. 5. Hourly produced PV power in the training dataset.

Table 3. Main characteristics of dataset

Characteristics	Power (W)	Insolation (W/m ²)	Temperature (C°)
Mean value	500	76	6
Min value	0	0	-15
Max value	5904	798	31
Time step	1 Hour		
Data length	3574 Hours		

Case 1:

The first training case will be for a Sugeno fuzzy model with three triangle membership functions for each input variable. The training result is shown in Fig 6. The evaluation of the generated model performance using the testing data is presented in Fig 7.

Fig. 6. Fuzzy surface map and membership functions (case 1), in which, “input1” is the insolation, “input2” is the temperature and “output” is the PV power

Fig. 7. Sugeno fuzzy model prediction performance (case 1)

Case 2:

In this case, a Sugeno fuzzy model is built using trapezoidal membership functions, two for insolation and three for temperature. The training result is shown in Fig 8. The evaluation of the generated model using the testing data is presented in Fig 9.

Fig. 8. Fuzzy surface map and membership functions (case 2), in which, “input1” is the insolation, “input2” is the temperature and “output” is the PV power

Fig. 10. Fuzzy surface map and membership functions (case 3), in which, “input1” is the insolation, “input2” is the temperature and “output” is the PV power

Fig. 9. Sugeno fuzzy model prediction performance (case 2)

Case 3:

In this case, a Sugeno fuzzy model with three Generalized bell-shape membership functions for each input variable. The training result is shown in Fig 10. The evaluation of the generated model using the testing data is presented in Fig 11.

Fig. 11. Sugeno fuzzy model prediction performance (case 3)

Comments:

Through previous results, it is clearly visible that the rapid alternance between snowing and sunny times makes a big confusion for all developed Sugeno fuzzy models. Even with a high accurate online weather forecast service at INES, the short cloudy periods (terms of hours) cannot be

efficiently predicted. In addition, during snowing days (Fig. 12), the snow can keep covering PV modules during the subsequent clear-sky days, provoking another challenge for standard ANFIS models to find out the real produced power, which is translated to big prediction errors visible in Fig. 7, Fig. 9 and Fig. 11, i.e., the snow layer on PV modules makes the solar cells not accessible for the solar irradiation.

Fig. 12. INES PV modules during a snowing day

IV. IMPROVED ANFIS

In this section, we will investigate the possibility to improve the developed standard ANFIS models to prevent the effect of the alternance snowing/sunny days. As mentioned previously, this improvement is based on adding historical power production evolution as a new input to the Sugeno fuzzy model. The reason behind this technique is to decrease or eliminate the impact of weather fluctuations on the performance of forecasting models. For this purpose, the average of historical produced power, for different horizons, is calculated. (Figs 13, 14 and 15).

Fig. 13. Average power production for the last 12 hours for every hourly value of training data.

Fig. 14. Average power production for the last 24 hours for every hourly value of training data.

Fig. 15. Average power production for the last 72 hours for every hourly value of training data

With the average of produced power for the last 12 hours as additional input, ANFIS model can have an information about the weather changes curve that has effect even in the current day. This is important when we aim to compensate the error caused by very short fluctuations on the insolation level due to the clouds movement. ANFIS will not track, with exactitude, the power to be produced, rather it will compensate the global forecast error caused by these fluctuations for one day scenario. This technique is suitable in case of daily energy management of PV/batteries hybrid system.

The radical climatic changes between snowing and sunny days has a slower dynamic compared to the insolation fluctuations. The ANFIS model can, with the average of produced power during the last 24 hours as additional input, improve the standard model in order to not rely solely on the online weather forecast service. This later usually cannot predict such rapid daily changes in weather conditions.

The average of produced power during the last 72 hours can give information about the weather trend in a general way and the state of the PV modules in particular. Adding it as an additional input to the ANFIS model, can provide significant improvement on the prediction performance as it offers information on the global weather trends regardless of the short-term weather fluctuations.

Case 4:

In this case, the training process will be carried out on a Sugeno fuzzy model with only two Generalized bell-shape membership functions for each input. The membership functions correspond to the trained improved ANFIS model are shown in Fig 16. The evaluation of the created model using the testing data is presented in Fig 17.

Fig. 16. Membership functions (case 4), in which, “input1” is the insolation, “input2” is the temperature, “input3” is the produced power average of the last 72 hours, and “output” is the PV power

Fig. 17. Sugeno fuzzy model prediction performance (case 4)

Comments:

Providing historical data, as additional input, improves significantly the forecasting accuracy as shown in Fig. 17. With information about the power production trend during the last 72 hours, along with real-time insolation and temperature data, the model is capable of decreasing the effect of fast changes in weather conditions. This can correct partially the problem of the inaccessibility of solar irradiation to the snow-covered PV modules.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, PV power forecast using improved ANFIS model is investigated. Standard models, which are based on the use of online services for weather data, cannot overcome the challenge of insolation fluctuations and the rapid changes in the general weather conditions. Adding the historical PV production power to the standard model, as an additional information to the weather data, can enhance significantly the ANFIS model performance, and even, detect critical situations like the effect of snows on PV modules during clear-sky days.

As a future work, the improved ANFIS model performance can be also evaluated in the context of PV models degradation impact. As it is well known, the operation degradation of PV cells can be accelerated under some specific conditions, mainly weather-related. The proposed ANFIS model can be tested in this regard using different historical data lengths. Obviously, the historical data in this case is significantly longer compared to the studied on in this article. The effect of adding different horizons can be also evaluated to find out the optimal input combination.

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